

Isoforms of cancer-related proteins tend to destabilize the structure

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Protein isoforms provide protein diversity through various biological mechanisms such as alternative splicing, alternative promoter usage and other mechanisms. Isoforms functions can differ depending on several factors, including their amino acid sequence and structure. Meanwhile, cancer-related protein isoforms have notable importance due to their association with the disease. Previous studies indicate that tumor suppressor protein p53 isoforms can either facilitate or inhibit tumor growth, depending on its isoform and the cellular context. However, earlier studies have mainly focused on investigating the structures of canonical proteins of cancer-related proteins, with relatively less attention given to the structural analysis of their isoforms. Determining the structure of isoforms of cancer-related proteins can be crucial for understanding the mechanisms of disease association. Changes in structure may affect the function of isoforms. Experimental studies can be expensive and time-consuming, frequently requiring significant resources to obtain accurate results. Nonetheless, recent advancements in structural biology, such as the AlphaFold tool, have provided a door of opportunity to study protein sequences deeply. Thanks to this tool, we can model highly accurate protein structures without the need for comprehensive laboratory research, allowing for more efficient and cost-effective research. Therefore, in our study, we implemented a comparative analysis of the canonical cancer-related proteins and their isoform structures made with AlphaFold to determine structural differences. Our analysis revealed that most of the isoforms of cancer-related proteins are more disordered than general protein isoforms.

Keywords: Protein structure, bioinformatics analysis, cancer-related proteins, isoform, AlphaFold

INTRODUCTION

Protein isoforms participate in crucial functions of various biological processes and many of them are also associated with diseases (Yamak et al., 2015; Sass, Comer and Searles, 1995; Pollenz, Necela and Marks-Sojka, 2002; Abiko et al., 2007). There are biological mechanisms such as alternative promoter usage, post-translational modifications and alternative splicing which are producing isoforms. Isoforms differ from their canonical (main protein which is widely expressed in different tissues) proteins in terms of expression level, structure and function. These differences may have significant importance for the regulation, maintenance and other processes of biological systems. Understanding the structural/functional roles of different isoforms is essential for explaining the mechanism of biological processes and identifying prospective therapeutic targets for

the disease. Previous studies claim that isoforms have been associated with diseases such as cancer, cardiovascular diseases, and neurological disorders. Targeting isoforms may provide opportunities to develop more effective and specific treatments for diseases (Zhang et al., 2013).

Earlier studies prove that isoforms play a role in cancer diseases. One of the known examples of cancer disease-associated isoforms is a p53-tumor suppressor protein. p53 has an essential role in the regulation of cell growth and prevention of oncogenesis (Bernard et al., 2013; Zhao and Sanyal, 2022). Certain isoforms of the p53 gene which are products of alternative splicing mechanisms play an active role in cancer development. For instance, previous studies found that the delta133p53 isoform of p53 is overexpressed in several types of cancer (Joruz et al., 2020). Another example of an isoform of cancer proteins is the HER2-human epidermal growth

factor receptor 2. Isoforms of HER2 differ by their domains which are located inside/outside of the cell and overexpressed in breast cancer (Palladini et al., 2017). Recently, studies of isoforms of cancer proteins became an interest-gaining area of research. Determining the structure of isoforms that are participated in cancer disease may provide new targets for clinical approaches. Nevertheless, there is still a huge gap between the number of isoform sequences and their structures. It is not possible experimentally resolve the mass number of structures of cancer-related proteins in terms of time and extensive expenses.

Nonetheless, recent improvements in the prediction of the protein structure provide an immense opportunity to obtain high-quality structural models of proteins. AlphaFold - a deep learning-based algorithm (Jumper et al., 2021) gives a possibility to gain insights into the molecular mechanisms. In addition, predicted models can be used to understand the effects of cancer-associated mutations on protein structure and function. In this study, we used the classification methods of our previous research on isoforms and applied them to isoforms of cancer-related proteins (Osmanli et al., 2022) by using the AlphaFold tool.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

In our analysis, we utilized data on 82 canonical cancer-related proteins and 166 corresponding isoforms, which was obtained from a previous study (Osmanli et al., 2022). To identify difference regions between the canonical and isoform proteins, we employed the Clustal Omega tool (Schütze et al., 2022). To ensure that our analysis was focused on structured regions with differences, we excluded protein pairs that had less than 10 amino acid differences in their difference regions, as well as those where the differences occurred at the N- and C-termini of the proteins. After applying our filtering criteria, we were left with 16 canonical proteins and 39 corresponding isoforms for further analysis. To obtain structural models for these proteins, we downloaded AlphaFold (Jumper et al., 2021) models for the canonical proteins from <https://alphafold.com/download#proteomes-section> (accessed on 14 April 2022), and predicted structures of their isoforms using AlphaFold Colab (Schütze et al., 2022). All structural models were analyzed by using the PyMol visualization tool (Schrödinger, 2015). To classify the structural states of both canonical proteins and their isoforms, we utilized classification rules described by Osmanli et al. (2022).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Our comparative analysis of the AlphaFold structures of 16 canonical proteins and their isoforms revealed that 8 pairs of canonical and isoform structures of different regions are unstructured. The remaining 31 canonical-isoform pairs were classified based on the rules outlined in the Materials and Methods section. Our results showed that among the difference regions in canonical-isoforms pairs, 26% did not affect the overall structure of the proteins - class 1, and 13% of substitutions preserve protein structure - class 2, while a majority of difference regions in isoforms of cancer proteins (58%) were found to destabilize the structure- class 4 (Fig. 1). We did not observe any cases of replacement or insertion of amino acid residues in the difference regions - class 3. Nevertheless, we determined one case (3%) where a deletion altered the protein structure.

Fig. 1. Classification of difference in structural states between canonical proteins of cancer-related genes and their isoforms. Class 1 - deletions do not affect the whole structure, Class 2 - substitutions conserve the whole structure, Class 3 - replacements of deletion with another part of the protein, Class 4 - deletions destabilize the structure, Special case - deletions alter the structure.

The preservation of structures in isoforms of cancer-related proteins may have a crucial role in understanding the underlying molecular mechanisms of cancer. Our results have shown that the total structure of cancer-related proteins in the analyzed set preserves only 26% of the isoforms, with deletions in alpha-helices being the most common. In most cases, these deletions do not affect the domains. For example, we observed deletions in the N-terminus of isoform model *Del40-p53beta* of the cellular tumor antigen p53 (Ghosh, Stewart and Matlashewski, 2004; Miki et al., 2013) (Fig. 2, Class 1) which plays a role in

breast cancer. It is known that these deletions affect the transcriptional activity of p53 (Bourdon et al., 2005), however, they do not disrupt the overall structural domains of the protein. Therefore, it is important to consider both the preservation of isoforms and the impact of deletions/substitutions on protein structure and function when studying cancer-related proteins.

Another class of the structural difference is the conservation of overall structure in the presence of the substitution. We observed that phenomenon only in repetitive proteins. C-Jun-amino-terminal

kinase-interacting protein play roles in the mediation of JNK signaling through aggregating specific components of the MAPK cascade (Bouwmeester et al., 2004), and overexpressed in different cancers (Brennan et al., 2020) (acute promyelocytic leukemia -AML, skin cancer). Isoform 6 (UniProt accession: O60271-9) of the following protein has substitutions at position 1175 and additional beta strands, although these changes do not alter the overall structure of the WD40 domain (Guinn et al., 2005) (Fig. 2, Class 2).

Fig. 2. AlphaFold structures of canonical proteins (on the left) and their isoforms (on the right) represented in ribbon models. Deleted parts in the isoform are marked in red, and inserted/substituted part is in yellow. P04637- cellular tumor antigen p53, deletion of alpha-helices does not affect the total structure of the protein, O60271- C-Jun-amino-terminal kinase-interacting protein 4, insertion of beta-strands does not change the whole structure of WD40 domain, O60524 - Ribosome quality control complex subunit NEMF, deleted beta-strands destabilize the structure of the protein, P04179 - Superoxide dismutase [Mn], mitochondrial, deletion reoriented the structure and isoform structure can make a dimer.

More than half of the structures of isoforms in our set are destructed by deletions. The findings are not consistent with the results of the previous large-scale analysis of the isoform sets (Osmanli et al., 2022) which may suggest that cancer disease-related isoforms have more potential for structural destabilization and deleterious effects in terms of the structure. For instance, ribosome quality control complex subunit NEMF (UniProt accession: O60524) has a role in lung cancer (Bi et al., 2005) and its isoform O60524-4 is destabilized by deletions at the positions 78-119, and 201-1076 (Fig. 2, Class 4). We have identified a specific case in which deletion has altered the orientation of the structure, suggesting that the dimeric form of the structure may potentially be its possible structure (Fig. 2, Special case). Mitochondrial superoxide dismutase [Mn] (UniProt accession: P04179) is an antioxidant enzyme that protects biological systems from oxidative stress caused by the production of superoxide anion radicals. This enzyme works by catalyzing the conversion of superoxide anion radicals into oxygen and hydrogen peroxide (MacMillan-Crow and Thompson, 1999).

In conclusion, our results suggest that more than half of cancer-related protein isoforms tend to be unstructured. The higher level of protein disorder in cancer-related isoforms could be associated with the disease. Taking into account that protein structure and function are linked, changes in protein structure can affect protein function, stability, and interactions with other molecules.

CONCLUSIONS

AlphaFold structural models of 39 cancer-related protein isoforms were generated and classified by their differences compared to their canonical proteins. It was found that the main part of the difference regions in cancer isoforms are unstructured in contrast to the previous studies in the larger set of proteins which included non-disease association. It may be linked to the disease association of the isoforms of the cancer proteins. Destabilization of the structure can lead to the loss of the complete or partial function, affecting the interactions with other molecules. The preservation of repetitive structure in the existence of the substitutions was also observed. Another interesting outcome was the preservation of alpha-helical structures in the presence of deletions. Additionally, the new

case determined which was exceptional for classification. In that case, the alteration changes the orientation of the structure.

The results suggest that alter in orientation may lead to forming a dimeric structure of the specific case. Therefore, further research would be required to establish a definitive relationship between protein disorders and cancer.

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Xərçənglə əlaqəli zülalların izoformlarının quruluşu destabilləşməyə meyllidir

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Zülal izoformaları alternativ splayinq, alternativ promotorlardan istifadə və digər mexanizmlər kimi müxtəlif bioloji mexanizmlər vasitəsilə zülal müxtəlifliyini təmin edir. İzoformaların funksiyaları bir neçə faktordan, o cümlədən onların amin turşusu ardıcılığından və strukturundan asılı olaraq fərqlənə bilər. Xərçənglə əlaqəli zülal izoformları xəstəliklə əlaqəli olduğuna görə xüsusi əhəmiyyət kəsb edir. Əvvəlki tədqiqatlar göstərir ki, p53 şiş supressoru zülalının izoformaları onun izoformundan və hüceyrə kontekstindən asılı olaraq şişin böyüməsini asanlaşdırır və ya əngəlləyə bilər. Bununla belə, əvvəlki tədqiqatlar əsasən xərçənglə əlaqəli zülalların kanonik zülallarının strukturlarının tədqiqinə yönəlmişdir və onların izoformalarının struktur analizinə nisbətən az diqqət yetirilmişdir. Xərçənglə əlaqəli zülalların izoformalarının strukturunun müəyyən edilməsi xəstəliyin birləşmə mexanizmlərini başa düşmək üçün çox vacib ola bilər. Strukturdakı dəyişikliklər izoformların funksiyasına təsir göstərə bilər. Eksperimental tədqiqatlar çox bahalı və vaxt aparan olur, dəqiq nəticələr əldə etmək üçün böyük resurslar tələb edir. Bu

baxımdan, struktur biologiyasında AlphaFold aləti kimi son nailiyyətlər zülal ardıcılıqlarını dərindən öyrənmək üçün geniş imkanlar açmışdır. Bu bioinformatik alət sayəsində biz hərtərəfli laboratoriya tədqiqatlarına ehtiyac olmadan yüksək dəqiqlikli zülal strukturlarını modelləşdirə, daha səmərəli və sərfəli tədqiqat apara bilərik. Buna görə də, bu araşdırmamızda izoformaların struktur fərqlərini müəyyən etmək üçün AlphaFold vasitəsi ilə kanonik xərçənglə əlaqəli zülalların və onların izoformalarının strukturlarının müqayisəli təhlili həyata keçirilmişdir. Təhlillərimiz göstərmişdir ki, xərçənglə əlaqəli zülalların izoformalarının əksəriyyəti ümumi protein izoformlarından daha nizamsızdır.

Açar sözlər: *Zülalın quruluşu, bioinformatik analiz, xərçənglə əlaqəli zülallar, izoforma, AlphaFold*